

Molding the Enablers of Corporate Sustainability Using Total Interpretive Structural Modeling

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ABSTRACT

In the time where sustainability strategies are increasingly becoming precursors to choose business priorities, there exists a need to understand the critical factors and their interdependencies, which could possibly influence the whole process. The aim of this paper is to build a hierarchical model with regard to the enablers of Corporate Sustainability (CS), using a Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) technique such as Total Interpretive Structural Modeling (TSIM). The present study identified a set of enablers with the most driving power and is visually represented with the help of a hierarchical model. Enablers of CS are extracted by critically examining the extant of available literature and through interviewing, brainstorming few experts from both industry practitioners and academia. In order to overcome the self-selection bias and respondent's bias, field survey was conducted using a structured questionnaire, with a sample size of 60 from the select pharmaceutical companies in India. Both the means are compared and there by the study follows a mixed mode research design. From the practitioner's lens, the study results an indicative list of enablers of CS for the pharmaceutical companies in India, at internal, external and connecting levels which enhances the organizational sustainability practices. Furthermore, the use of TISM as a methodology to perform exploratory study, to identify the variables of interest and represent their interactions using hierarchical structures envelopes the academic implications and also acts as a guide line for the industry practitioners.

Key words Corporate Sustainability, Total interpretive structural modeling (TISM), Indian Pharmaceutical Industry, Decision Making, MCDM.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has become the buzzword of the 21st century which emphasizes the need of giving by the corporate companies towards the welfare of the society. Corporate Sustainability (OS) in the contemporary business paradigms is understood more as a Triple Bottom Line (TBL) approach than the endurance aspect of sustainability. Dyllick and Hockerts (2002) explained CS as a business strategy which aims to fulfill the needs of the organizational stakeholders and at the same time, not compromising the interests and resources of the local community (IISD *et al.*, 1992). Sustainable Business

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Management is the ability to manage the relationships in order to address the societal, ecological and economic demands from the internal and external stakeholders (van Kleef and Roome, 2007, p. 44). The whole idea of corporate sustainability is to side line the notion of profit as a bottom line and adds the societal and ecological stand points to the current main stream reporting. The phrase ‘responsibility’ of the business towards the society is understood in a very narrow fashion as it is just another lane to discard the unconstructive effects of the business. Theories or approaches build upon this notion are vibrant over short period of time. Conversely, the broad understating of the term ‘Responsibility’ investigates the integrative view of all the challenges and opportunities which results not only an efficient but also an effective organization (Dyllick and Hockerts, 2002), thereby creating value for the organization as a whole and the society. The relationship between business and society has undergone major changes from the last two decades in various parts of the world including India. CSR demonstrates the social commitment by the businesses towards the society (Majumdar & Saini, 2013).

In order to achieve corporate Sustainability, there are four different types of strategies (Schaltegger and Wagner, 2006; Baumgartner & Ebner, 2010) which are 1) Introverted 2) Extroverted 3) Conservative and 4) Visionary. Progressive instructions to deals with the conundrum of enhancing social, ecological, and economic objectives all the while is one of the organization's greatest difficulties. Economic aspect of sustainability deals the bottom line and the flow of money. It is generally measured by using organizational performance as a measure especially in the domains of human resource management and strategic management. Furthermore, economic sustainability is expected to maximize value creation and living standards by extenuating its operational costs (Fowler and Hope, 2007). Social aspect of sustainability is often referred by the much popular term, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). The effectiveness of the CSR activities of an organization is measured by Corporate Social Performance. Social variables include the measurements of health and well being, quality of life, education etc of a community or a region. Addressing social issues by a corporate is possible by practicing and internalizing the aspect of ethical behavior into the firm's business process and practices (Baumgartner and Ebner, 2010; Bansal, 2005). The third dimension of the triple bottom line is the environmental sustainability, which reflects the organization's influence on the surrounding natural resources and its viability. An effective Environmental Management Program (EMP) is to be framed by all the organizations to mitigate resource consumption, ecological foot print and environmental pollution within their respective carrying capacity (Lindgreen et al. 2009; Linnenluecke et al. 2007; Hart 1995). Incorporating organizational social, ecological, and economic effects into operational and capital investment choices accompanies a considerable measure of strain. While social and monetary activities may profit each other in the long haul, they frequently tend to clash in their requirement for assets and plans in the short run. Additionally, clear, measurable, fleeting measurements apply to economic related activities, while estimations of social execution are regularly questionable. They are questionable due to the nascent stage of standardized (widely accepted) measures and metrics of social sustainability and long haul due to the amount of time that a social activity takes from ideation to value offering stage. For instance, Steurer et al. (2005) recognized economic related execution, long haul competition, and hierarchical monetary or budgetary effect on stakeholders as the key financial issues of sustainability. Expanding on this exploration, Choi and Ng (2011), affirm that financial maintainability is concerned with monetary prosperity and expectation for everyday life, and with it's reflect picture: Loss of Employment, frailty, and financial insecurity. Pfeffer (2010) underlined the vitality of dealing with the human capital, to preserve and evade squander in operations, thereby diminishing the trouble of economic activity on the environment and generate

ecological integrity. Economic inequality, environmental degradation and societal concerns have given added strength to the notion of studying the relationships between sustainability and organizational practices. Much of the challenge lies in the quantitative measurement of the tri pronged sustainability. Researchers advocated that a common measure to compare all the three dimensions would create tensions and externalities to the organizations. An innovative index is much needed which gives equal weighing to all three standalone pillars of sustainability. Sustainability metrics and sustainability analytics is the way forward. By now, it is understandable that the research area of sustainability is quite latest in terms of the academic literature, a felt need in the industry due to the limited talent pool with regard to the sustainability value chain, and more over the timeliness and research gaps makes a strong impact to conduct the research in this sub area of strategic management.

The present study identifies the enablers of corporate sustainability based on the extensive literature review and total interpretive structural modeling is used to represent the set of enablers in a hierarchical framework. Further sections elucidate the review of literature, research methodology followed by discussions, implications and conclusions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sustainability as a phrase is adequately known in terms of its environmental dimension, soon after the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) provided a definition to it in the year 1987 (United Nations Documents 1987). According to WCED, sustainability is defined as the ability to meet the needs of the present generation without comprising the needs of the present generation. Corporate Sustainability is one of the recent business advances from mere environmental sustainability, which instantiates long-term consumer and employee value thereby creating a social, cultural, and economic environment. CS also articulates strategies to build an organization that can experience a long term competitive advantage through employee development and transparency. In line to this, the concept of Triple Bottom Line (TBL) was developed by Elkington (2004, 2006), who described that the goals of business should be inseparable to the goals of societies and the environment in which they operate. TBL underlines the importance of short term economic gain as well as the cost of the failure to account for environmental and societal impacts. Gray (2010) provided a much broader definition to sustainability as a systems based concept. Crux of sustainability as proposed by Aras and Crowther (2008) boils down to wards the efficiency in the transformation process of the organization and equity in the distributive effects. And more over majority of the research work carried out so far in field of sustainability is mostly conceptual in nature, leaving much scope for empirical investigations to test and validate interesting relationships (Hart and Dowell, 2010). In lieu of this, researchers like Ina Ehnert (2006, 2009), made an attempt to apply this concept of sustainability is primarily focused environmental dimension from an organizational stand point. This took place in the early 21st century. Stakeholders believe that the organization needs to focus on their growth parallel to the growth of the society (Cohen 2010). The sustainability practices performed by the organizations are to be communicated effectively to their key stakeholders. This process is termed as sustainability reporting. In addition to the fiscal display of the company's balance sheet, there is an increasing demand and felt need for the sustainability reports (Sandhu & Kapoor, 2010).

Lankoski (2000) carried out a path breaking study which opened the doors for CS research across different corporate sectors. He examined the influence of industries and time on environmental profit (expected profit earned out of reducing affluent discharges). The relationship between societal and financial performance paved the

way towards introducing Corporate Social Responsibility and Corporate Social Performance (Carroll, 1999; Wood & Jones, 1995). Similarly, Pava and Krausz (1996) underlined the evidence for the positive association between the firm's environmental and financial performance. Incorporating environmental issues as part of the company's business practices in order to gain competitive advantage has become the contemporary business strategy. Nevertheless, the exhaustive set of all the environmental proactiveness indicators is not yet identified (Mitra, 2011). Lozano, (2012) also posited that as per the academic literature, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) occupies the quality share for the genesis of corporate sustainability. CS has emerged as an alternative to CSR by borrowing most of its vocabulary (Dyllick & Hockerts, 2002) and is currently considered as a business case (the precursor of doing business). CSR is an offshoot of ethical business practices and is further influenced by corporate governance practices. Corporate governance and corporate reporting practices are influenced by the multi dimensional cultural factors such as human rights, labor and anti corruption issues (Wise & Ali, 2008).

Past literature suggests a paradox that there are adequate number empirical studies conducted on CS, but most of the contemporary studies still measure the CS dimensions qualitatively based on the company declarations such as annual reports (Chan 2005; Steurer et al. 2005; Chang and Kuo 2008; Lindgreen et al. 2009). This process underlines the limitation of addressing successful of CS practices within the organization and across the industry (Labuschagne et al. 2005). By now, it can be understood that CS strategies are very important for any successful business establishment. The authors in the present study attempt to analyze the enablers of CS. There are quite a number of studies which focused in enumerating the enablers of CS (DeSimone & Popoff, 2000) and the subsequent sections explain the classification of enablers in detail.

3. ENABLERS OF CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY

The efforts of Corporate Sustainability has been largely taken up by the large Multinational companies and whereas the Small and Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) making the complimentary efforts (C.E.C., 2001, 2002; Farmer & Hogue, 1973). Civil society, Government and Corporations encompasses the tri-pronged approach which fosters the organizational sustainability initiatives. There are myriad of factors which drive the CS efforts and can be divided broadly into External (or) Extramural and Internal (or) Intramural enablers. DeSimone & Popoff (2000) explained the external enablers of CS are more reactive in nature and would be less likely to make the organization move towards sustainability. Corporate Brand Reputation (Oskarsson & von Malmborg, 2005; Quazi, 2001; Dunphy, et al., 2003; Hopkins, 2002), Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), Government Policies (Dunphy, et al., 2003; McIntosh, et al.,1998; Atkinson, 2000), Market Expectations (McIntosh, et al., 1998, Biscaccianti, 2003; Dunphy, et al., 2003) Stakeholder Pressures (Frehs, 2003; Zadek, 1999), Competitors Benchmarking (McIntosh, Leipziger, & Jones, 1998; Quazi, 2001), Customer Satisfaction (Frankental, 2001; Laffer, et al., 2004) are some of the External enablers. Internal or Intramural enablers are more of proactive in nature. Ethical Leadership (Szekely & Knirsch, 2005), Corporate Image Enhancement (Frehs, 2003), Protection of Business Reputation (Lantos, 2001), Economic Value Improvements (Carroll, 1999), Resources and Cost Savings (Henriques & Richardson, 2005; Quazi, 2001), Profits and Growth (Frehs, 2003; Laffer, et al., 2004) and Employee Shared Values (Frankental, 2001; Frehs, 2003; Quazi, 2001), Leadership (Gill, 2003; Porter & van der Linde, 2000); Quality (Laffer, et al., 2004; Quazi, 2001) are some of the pivotal Internal enablers of CS practices. A close observation of the literature related to the

enablers of CS practices results that, the key external and internal enablers occurred to be almost equal in number. In the present study, rather than classifying the enablers into external and internal, the most important of them are taken as a single set (to avoid the repetitiveness of applying TISM twice for each external and internal set of enablers) followed by the application of Total Interpretive Structural Modeling. The importance of the enablers was found out by the extensive literature review (based on the number of times a respective enabler is discussed), and due consultation with three academicians and four industry practitioners.

3.1. Corporate Brand Reputation

Alike every company, corporate identity plays an important role in formulating the company's sustainability strategy. The most common factor is to maintain cultural and traditional values. Most companies are either fighting market downturns or in the mode of rapid economic development. Both situations create opportunities and challenges for the region they operate in. Preserving brand and reputation in precarious times is even more important than in times of prosperity (Argenti & Druckenmiller, B. 2004). Brand loyalty among employees and customers can be tested by analyzing the extent to which customers and employees adopt the company's sustainability principles in their daily lives (De Chernatony, 1999).

3.2. Competitors Benchmarking

Corporate sustainability initiatives mitigate environmental and reputational risks and can help companies drive business upside by redesigning processes, product offerings and business models to gain a real competitive edge (Wolfram Cox et al., 1997). But how can companies know whether their organizational sustainability strategies are in fact effective? This is where competitive benchmarking comes in. What does this entail? Simply put, benchmarking means learning from the best in order to improve one's own performance. Benchmarking arms organizations with information about what is happening in the marketplace, including which strategies work and which don't (Elnathan et al., 1996). Most importantly, it highlights ways to improve sustainability performance and helps companies demonstrate the positive impact of their CS strategies on their financial results.

3.3. Media Attention

Media can play an important role in mobilizing social movements such as environmental interest groups. It can also assign importance to some issues and expose gaps in others. In doing so, it becomes part of the institution-building process, shaping the norms of acceptable and legitimate sustainable development practices. According to Simon (1992), the media is the main source of environmental information. The media not only plays a passive role in shaping institutional norms, but also a more active one by choosing the stories worth reporting and framing them to reflect editorial values. Empirical studies have shown that the media has been particularly influential on organizational environmental responses (Bowen, 2000; Bansal and Clelland, 2004; Bansal and Roth, 2000). The total amount of media coverage raises the firm's visibility, inviting further public attention and scrutiny. The threat of negative media publicity can apply coercive pressure on firms to commit sustainable development activities by eroding the legitimacy of a firm if the media finds some practices unacceptable.

3.4. Shareholder Activism

Shareholder activism is defined as the use of ownership position to actively influence company policy and practice (Smith, 1996). Shareholder activism can be exerted through letter writing, through dialogue with organizational management or the board, through asking questions at open sessions at annual general meetings and through the filing of formal shareholder proposals. Researchers have studied shareholder activism for organizational social and environmental responsibility for a number of years now, from different angles and with different approaches (Gillan & Starks, 2000). It is therefore time to sum up, and to explore what we have learnt on this topic so far.

3.5. Innovation

Many companies discovered innovative solutions to other aspects, like diversification of energy procurement portfolio, introduction of effective monitoring procedures and improvement of operational efficiency. In many such ways, companies can redefine their organic growth plans by designing more effective, efficient, sustainable products, or operations that cater to changing social and economic challenges of a region (Burns & Stalker, 1961). Solutions where the value generated accrues to society primarily, rather than meeting individual needs they might attract government support as well (Utterback & Abernathy, 1975). Innovation could be bidirectional, both in operations and product design. For example, the environmental concerns of a country could inspire companies to launch eco-friendly products or buying methods. Similarly, solutions to the neighborhood's social problems could resolve an organization's pertinent human resource issues.

3.6. Fines and Penalties

Institutional processes can work through coercive pressures imposed by institutions that directly influence firms (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Failing to comply to these pressures, particularly those imposed by urgent and powerful stakeholders, can result in loss of earnings, a damaged reputation, or even loss of the license to operate (Oliver, 1991; Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). Every person interviewed spoke to the role of government in influencing corporate sustainable development. Firms that have previously incurred fines are scrutinized closely by the government and special interest groups for further indiscretions because of their loss of legitimacy (Meyer and Rowan, 1991). In an effort to deflect this scrutiny, these firms will subscribe to a higher standard of corporate sustainable development. Firms that have been subject to fines and penalties will also become more sensitive to acceptable sustainable development practices and be more informed of what they need to do to avoid further infractions.

3.7. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction holds an important part in corporate strategies and acts as the key driver of firm's long term profitability and market value. The more a customer purchases and consumes a product, the more satisfied he is. With latest advancement in strategic management literature, it has been proved that CSR initiatives also induce more customer satisfaction. Maignan et al., (2005), on the basis of stakeholder's theory and institutional theory proved that company's actions appeals to multidimensional aspect of consumers along with their family and communities. Daub and Ergenzinger (2005) proposed that companies need to consider not only the generalized customers, but also the prospective members of various stakeholders. This is because customers like those products which has positive social image.

3.8. Employee Shared Values

The concept of shared value enhances the organizational policies and practices so as to increase the competitiveness of the company with advancing social and economic conditions in the society in which the company sells and operates (Porter & Kramer, 2011). Designing novel products and services to meet social and environmental requirements along with delivering financial outcomes and profits, contact new markets, tap new and better resources and partners to increase productivity by reconfiguring and protecting value chain (Pfitzer et al., 2013). Additionally, collaborate with executive teams and individual champions regarding organizational affairs and sustainability.

3.9. Personnel Engagement

Studies ascertained that employees prefer challenging and meaningful job to attain higher degree of job satisfaction, work engagement, commitment and give their best to the organization. Therefore, employers should attempt to provide jobs to their employees that is more challenging and provides them an opportunity to learn and grow (Johnstone & Bedard, 2001). This can enable employees to stay internally motivated. Contrary to this, if the job is monotonous and provides lesser options for learning and development, then the level of motivation among employees decline (Christian et al., 2011). Even the scholars from Harvard Business review and Boston University School of Management, proposed to harness the organizational members internally to let them stay engaged to their work roles.

3.10. Social Legitimacy

Many organizations' enter into CSR activities in order to fulfill their social legitimacy. Studies incorporate that organization take different strategies to attain legitimacy which can enable them to emphasize more on CSR activities. Though initially, scholars considered CSR as comprising actions like incorporating greater environmental and safety provisions and charitable contributions, which focused more on organizational motives to take CSR initiatives and the implications of organizational performance on CSR actions. Bansal and Roth (2000) showed that by improving legitimacy, firms can get stakeholders approval for long term sustainability, and gain employee job satisfaction. Additionally, organizations can adopt philanthropy as it will help them to expand sociopolitical legitimacy, which directs them to bring out positive stakeholder responses and increases political access.

3.11. Proactive Ethical Leadership

To take organizational social responsibility, leaders must also take significant proactive ethical steps. Scholars propose that effective execution of organizational social responsibility can support ethical leadership and enable leaders to take proactive steps (Brown & Treviño, 2006). Organizations need to deploy their leaders' capabilities to influence employee value propositions and proactively support organizational social responsibilities, to accomplish stakeholder's expectations.

3.12. Market Expectations

Uncertainty in market poses several problems for the firms. To reduce it firms try to imitate the similar firms (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983), and capitalize peer's success and mark sustainable development. Sustainable development is the only resort, as expectations are changing, and the complexity of problems is increasing and the resolving it is becoming a difficulty for managers. Therefore, to take the advantage, firms impersonate visible and well defined activities of others like environment audits. This is done specifically when such activities have been reported to others. While doing

so, organizations must consider the corporate social responsibility that they have towards economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary expectations of all stakeholders (Carroll, 1979). In this respect, Wood’s framework for socially responsible processes has attained the maximum grip in business research (Hillman and Keim, 2001; Swanson, 1995; Waddock and Graves, 1997).

Figure 1: Process of OS-TISM

4. METHODOLOGY

The present study attempts to investigate the 12 selected enablers which influence the corporate sustainability practices. In order to understand and interpret the linkages among these 12 enablers, a multi criteria decision making technique named Total Interpretive Structural Modeling (TISM) is used, by collecting and analyzing the responses from both the industry and academic experts. The respondents were chosen from the select pharmaceutical companies which operating mostly in the southern region of India by the convenience based sampling technique. In general, there are many enablers who could possibly influence the CS practices and can also be classified into various categories such as internal, external, major and minor affects so on and so forth. It would be highly challenging for any organization to track and take care of all of them amidst the dynamic business environment. In lieu of this, the present study

attempts to fulfill the felt need to build a hierarchical model, which signifies the relative importance of the enablers that are to be given due importance, so that necessary investments and cost cutting can be made accordingly. To achieve this objective, all the possible drivers affecting the organizational sustainability are found based on the secondary data such as Journals, websites, books and other databases related to business and management studies. The key words used to the secondary data are ‘enablers of sustainability practices’, ‘enablers/antecedents of corporate sustainability’, so on and so forth. This process resulted in 32 significant enablers and out of which with due consultation of industry and academic experts, and the complexity of TISM algorithm with respect to the number of input variables they were further short-listed to 12 enablers. The present study attempts to investigate the effect of these 12 enablers on corporate sustainability practices is to be studied using TISM.

4.1 Methodology

Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) from the class of structural models is a precursor to the TISM, which helps to contextually interpret the relationship and direction between any two given variables of interest. The aspect of casual thinking behind confirming the association between the variables is the limitation possessed by the ISM and same is the advancement and rationale shown in building the qualitative modeling technique of TISM (Sushil, 2005). Interpretive matrix plays the key role in the TISM approach to build the casual thinking (Sushil, 2005) behind the rationale of the experts, which in simple terms answers the question “Why the relationship exists between the two variables?” TISM approach begins with the identification of the required variables as per the given context of the study and continues with the group solving technique followed by a contextually related subordinate solution. Once the contextual relation and the element set are chosen, a structural self-interaction matrix is framed using the method of pair wise comparison between the variables. Subsequently, the structural self-interaction matrix is transformed into a reachability matrix and the transitivity is checked resulting in a structural model which is called the interpretive structural model.

4.2 Analysis & Results

The 12 enablers of organizational sustainability which epitomize the focal point of the present study are defined as V1, V2, V3.....V12. The relationships among all these variables are represented using matrix format, in which the variables occupying the rows are identified with i and column variables with j. As the relationship between any two variables changes with respect to the associated direction, we have codified the possible types of association that can exist between any two variables using the symbols V, A, O and X. The symbol represent, V: When i leads to j but j does not lead to i; A- When j leads to i but i does not lead to j; X- When I leads to j and j leads to i; O- When there is no relationship between the variables. The matrix which is formed out of codifying the relationships between any two given variables using the symbols such as V, A, X and O is called as the Structural Self Interaction Matrix (SSIM). The responses resulted out of all the pair wise interaction among the 12 variables is recorded in the SSIM, which is represented in the Table 1 here in under.

Table 1. Structural Self-Interaction Matrix

Code	Variable	V12	V11	V10	V9	V8	V7	V6	V5	V4	V3	V2	V1
V1	Corporate Brand Reputation	V	X	V	O	X	A	O	V	O	A	A	...
V2	Competitors Benchmarking	O	V	A	V	O	V	A	X	A	O	...	
V3	Media Attention	V	O	X	A	V	O	X	A	O	...		
V4	Shareholder Activism	A	V	O	X	O	V	A	A	...			
V5	Innovation	A	O	V	A	A	O	V	...				
V6	Fines & Penalties	V	A	X	A	V	O	...					
V7	Customer Satisfaction	O	A	V	O	A	...						
V8	Employee Shared Values	O	O	A	O	...							
V9	Personnel Engagement	O	A	A	...								
V10	Social Legitimacy	V	X	...									
V11	Proactive Ethical Leadership	O	...										
V12	Market Expectations	...											

4.2.1 Reachability Matrix (RM)

Reachability Matrix is helpful to transform the codified structural self-interaction matrix into binary digits, which in turn simplifies the process of building the hierarchical TISM model. The pattern in which the codified relationships between the variables are converted to binary is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Rule for transforming SSIM to RM

I-J Entry	I to J Relation	J to I Relation
V	1	0
A	0	1
X	1	1
O	0	0

Table 3. Reachability Matrix

Code	V01	V02	V03	V04	V05	V06	V07	V08	V09	V10	V11	V12
V01	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1
V02	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
V03	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
V04	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
V05	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
V06	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
V07	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
V08	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
V09	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
V10	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1
V11	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
V12	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1

4.2.2 Partitioning the Reachability Matrix

The reachability matrix was partitioned into different levels to build the order of importance among from the identified 12 enablers of Corporate Sustainability. The hierarchical structure was built using the levels that the variables occupied. Reachability

set (RS) encompasses all the variables which possess the value 1 in its respective row with respect to our variable of interest and Antecedent Set (AS) encompasses all the variables which possess the value 1 in its column with respect to our variable of interest (Sushil, 2012). The variable was taken to the higher level, if the intersection of RS & AS is same as RS and it was taken out before we proceed to the next iteration (Sushil, 2012). The same process was repeated till all the 12 variables were exhausted from the pipeline, which results in a top to down hierarchical structure of all the twelve enablers influencing CS practices, is represented as part of Table 4.

Table 4. Level partition of variables

Variable	Reachability Set (RS)	Antecedent Set (As)	AS U RS	Level
Iteration 1				
V1	1,5,8,10,11,12	1,3,5,8,10,11,12	1,5,8,10	I
V2	2,5,7,9,11	2,6,9	2,9	
V3	1,3,6,8,10,12	3,4,6,8,10	3,6,8,10	
V4	3,4,7,9,11	4,7,11,12	4,7,11	
V5	1,5,6,10	1,2,5,9	1,5	
V6	2,3,6,10,12	3,5,6,8,10,12	3,6,10,12	
V7	4,7,10	2,4,7,9,10	4,7,10	I
V8	1,3,6,8,10	1,3,8,11	1,3,8	
V9	2,5,7,9	2,4,9	2,9	
V10	1,3,6,7,10,11,12	1,3,5,6,7,8,10,11,12	1,3,6,7,10,11,12	I
V11	1,4,8,10,11	1,2,4,10,11	1,4,10,11	
V12	1,4,6,10,12	1,3,6,10,12	1,6,10,12	
Iteration 2				
V2	2,5,9,11	2,6,9	2,9	
V3	3,6,8,12	3,4,6,8	3,6,8	
V4	3,4,9,11	4,11,12	4,11	
V5	5,6	2,5,6,9	5,6	II
V6	2,3,5,6,8,12	3,5,6,8,12	3,5,6,8,12	
V8	3,6,8	3,6,8,11	3,6,8	II
V9	2,5,9	2,4,9	2,9	
V11	4,8,11	2,4,11	4,11	
V12	4,6,12	3,6,12	6,12	
Iteration 3				
V2	2,9,11	2,6,9	2,9	
V3	3,6,12	3,4,6	3,6	
V4	3,4,9,11	4,11	4,11	
V6	2,3,6,12	3,6,12	3,6,12	
V9	2,9	2,4,9	2,9	III
V11	4,11	2,4,11	4,11	III
V12	4,6,12	3,6,12	6,12	
Iteration 4				
V2	2	2,6	2	IV

V3	3,6,12	3,4,6	3,6	
V4	3,4	4,12	4	
V6	2,3,6,12	3,6,12	3,6,12	
V12	4,6,12	3,6,12	6,12	
Iteration 5				
V3	3,6,4	3,4,6,12	3,4,6	V
V4	3,4	4,12	4	
V6	3,6,12	3,6,12	3,6,12	V
V12	3,4,6,12	3,6,12	3,6,12	
Iteration 6				
V4	4	4,12		VI
V12	4,12	12		
Iteration 7				
V12	4,12	12	12	VII

Table 5. Variable Levels

No	Variable	Code	Level
1	Corporate Brand Reputation	V1	I
2	Competitors Benchmarking	V7	I
3	Media Attention	V10	I
4	Shareholder Activism	V5	II
5	Innovation	V8	II
6	Fines & Penalties	V9	III
7	Customer Satisfaction	V11	III
8	Employee Shared Values	V2	IV
9	Personnel Engagement	V3	V
10	Social Legitimacy	V6	V
11	Proactive Ethical Leadership	V4	VI
12	Market Expectations	V12	VII

4.2.3 Diagram with Significant Transitive Links

The elements are arranged graphically in levels and the directed and significant links are shown as per the relationships observed in the reachability matrix. Figure 1 below gives the diagrammatic representation of total interpretive model obtained from the study.

Fig 2: TISM Model

5. VALIDATION OF TISM

TISM algorithm reported 19 significant links among the CS enablers in consensus with the experts and the related literature. In order to further validate the rankings generated by the TISM algorithm, a questionnaire based survey was also developed and circulated via online medium. In total 75 respondents were chosen as a representative sample, serving at the top and middle level management positions in the high performing pharmaceutical companies operating in the southern part of the India. Pharmaceutical industry provides the most lucrative and life saving products. According to World Health Organization (2014), ten large drug companies control near about one-third of the market. In lieu of this, the pharmaceutical compounds along with its product disposal and discharge have become a serious concern to the environment (Pandya Amit, & Mavani Prati, 2012). This has lead to the interest of research community to the corporate sustainability aspects of pharmaceutical companies (Page et al., 2015). Hence, based on the above presented evidence the authors have chosen pharmaceutical sector as the population of the study.

The 7 point likert scale from Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Disagree Somewhat, Undecided, Agree Somewhat, Agree and Strongly Agree was used as a survey method

of analysis. It tends to be relevant because, the TISM algorithm was formulated with the consultation of few experts and more inclined towards the secondary data. As a support study, a relatively less number of respondents also serve the purpose. A true blend of quantitative and qualitative techniques on a particular scenario, results in an accurate and generalizable findings (Shah and Corley, 2006).

In order to perform the quantitative testing, null and alternative hypotheses were formulated which are mentioned here in under.

H₀. There is no significant difference between the observed and specified mean from the view of the current experts.

H₁. There is a significant difference between the observed and specified mean from the view of the current experts.

The hypothesis testing was performed using one sample t-test where in the test value was set at 5.5. It can be deciphered from table no 6 that out of the total 20 direct links resulted from the TISM algorithm, the links 5, 8 and 10 were non-significant and the remaining 17 are significant at the 5% level of significance. Table 6 shows the quantitative verification of the links among the twelve enablers of organizational sustainability.

Table 6. Statistical comparison

Link No	Enablers Linked	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig*	Accept Reject
Link 1	Market Expectations on Shareholder Activism	5.58	0.91	7.50066	0.01	Accept
Link2	Shareholder Activism on Media Attention	5.12	0.86	4.55628	0.00	Accept
Link 3	Shareholder Activism on Fines Penalties	4.85	0.73	3.03014	0.02	Accept
Link 4	Media Attention on Competitors Benchmarking	4.91	0.87	2.97839	0.00	Accept
Link 5	Media Attention on Fines and Penalties	4.28	0.71	6.38221	0.32	Reject
Link 6	Fines and Penalties on Competitors Benchmarking	5.34	0.62	8.56258	0.00	Accept
Link 7	Competitors Benchmarking on Personnel Engagement	5.12	0.91	4.30593	0.04	Accept
Link 8	Competitors Benchmarking on Proactive Ethical Leadership	4.35	0.95	-0.9979	0.21	Reject
Link 9	Personnel Engagement on Innovation	5.85	1.02	8.36471	0.02	Accept
Link 10	Proactive Ethical Leadership on Employee Shared Values	4.24	0.77	-2.134	0.17	Reject
Link 11	Innovation on Brand Reputation	5.72	0.88	8.76182	0.01	Accept
Link 12	Innovation on Customer Satisfaction	6.21	0.93	11.6206	0.02	Accept
Link 13	Employee Shared Values on Customer Satisfaction	4.56	0.82	0.46244	0.03	Accept
Link 14	Employee Shared Values on	5.43	0.72	8.16333	0.00	Accept

	Social Legitimacy					
Link 15	Corporate Brand Reputation on Customer Satisfaction	5.65	0.64	11.3563	0.00	Accept
Link 16	Corporate Brand Reputation on Social Legitimacy	5.92	0.56	16.0257	0.02	Accept
Link 17	Customer Satisfaction on Corporate Brand Reputation	4.89	1.09	2.26128	0.00	Accept
Link 18	Customer Satisfaction on Social Legitimacy	5.45	1.12	5.36071	0.00	Accept
Link 19	Social Legitimacy on Customer Satisfaction	6.32	0.43	26.7498	0.00	Accept
Link 20	Social Legitimacy on Corporate Brand Reputation	5.21	0.77	5.82753	0.00	Accept

*Significance: one-tailed.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study has taken a new effort altogether by constructing an interactive, hierarchical, and a qualitative framework using the enablers of CS by TISM methodology, in the context of select Indian pharmaceutical companies. TISM is a methodology which has been in use to identify and summarize the relationships among the significant enablers which are considered for the study. Enablers of OS were extracted using relevant literature review and Content Analysis of the semi structured interviews which were conducted with Middle level and top level managers from the select pharmaceutical companies in India. A hierarchical TISM model was built with respect to the priority given by the respondents and mean was computed. In order to overcome the self-selection bias and respondent's bias, field survey was performed using a structured questionnaire, with a sample size of 60 and mean was computed. Hypotheses results have shown that except three, all the linkages are statistically significant. The linkages such as Media Attention on Fines and Penalties, Competitors Benchmarking on Proactive Ethical Leadership and Proactive Ethical Leadership on Employee Shared Values are insignificant. The reason being, all the three linkages are not irreversible in nature i.e. employee shared values stimulates proactive ethical leadership but the vice versa is less likely to happen (Brown & Treviño, 2006). This indicate that the three pairs of drivers though individually contribute as enabling factors to organizational sustainability but doesn't have intra associations. The study presents a priority chart of internal, external and connecting enablers of CS of an organization which aims to achieve economic prosperity, environmental integrity and social equity. This study highlights implications for academicians as well as practitioners. From the practitioner's lens, the study results an indicative list of enablers of CS for the pharmaceutical companies in India, at internal, external and connecting levels which enhances the organizational effectiveness. The use of TISM as a methodology to perform exploratory study and to identify some of the variables of interest in order to represent their interactions through hierarchical structures is some of the academic implications. 12 enablers of CS were only considered to build the TISM model and the response bias of the experts consulted to map the conceptual relationship among the 12 enablers could be a limitation of the present study. The authors would be using Structural Equation Modeling to validate the proposed structure statistically as their subsequent research contributions.

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